

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2018-19 academic year for BPT

BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID

**COLLEGE OF
PHYSIOTHERAPY**
Value Added Course
**BASIC NURSING &
FIRST AID**

**FOR BPT (2018 BATCH)
UNDERGRADUATES**

**Learn Lifesaving Skills
From the Experts**

Course Duration: 40 hours

CONTACT
College of Physiotherapy, Ground floor, Srinivas
University City campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru
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Course period	From January 2019 till March 2019, during 2 nd semester (10 weeks)
Duration	40 hours (4 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	BPT 1 st year undergraduates (2018 batch)

Course Objectives:

- Understand the new responsibilities of an Occupational First Aider.
- To be familiar with health & safety legislation on first aid in the workplace (e.g. Contents of First Aid Box)

Course Outline:

Week	Lectures	Assignments	Hour ¹
Module 1 «Introduction to nursing and nursing positions»			
1-2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is nursing? Nursing principles. Inter personnel relationships. Basic turns: Bandaging extremities: Triangular Bandages and their application. • Nursing position: Environment safety: Bed making, prone, lateral, dorsal, dorsal recumbent, Flower's positions, comfort measures, Aids and rest and sleep. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Home assignments ✓ Lab: Practice of nursing positions 	8
Module 2 «Bedside management and methods of Nourishment»			
3-5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bed side Management: Giving and taking Bed pan, Urinal: Observation of stools, Urine. Observation of Sputum, Understand use and care of care of catheters, enema giving • Lifting and transporting patients: Lifting patient up in the bed, transferring from bed to wheel chair, transferring from bed to stretcher • Methods of giving Nourishment: Feeding, tube feeding, Tube feeding, drips, transfusion. • Observation of surgical procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Assignments ✓ Lab: Practice sessions 	12
Module 3 «First Aid»			

6-7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of first aid in physiotherapy • Instrumentation used in First Aid (First Aid kit) • Examination of Vital signs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Home Assignments ✓ Lab: Demonstrations and practice 	8
Module 4 «First Aid procedures»			
8-10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Aid in cardiac arrest and in Respiratory failure • First Aid in Burns, Electric shock, Hypovolemic shock and Drowning • First Aid in Spinal cord injuries; Poisoning; RTA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Demonstrations and case studies 	12

¹ Hours designed for Classroom sessions, video tutorials, Home Assignments, Activities etc.

Attendance Policy

The course requires compulsory 75% attendance and only in this case a student will be issued a certificate.

Book References:

1. I Clement. Text book on First Aid & Emergency Nursing. Jaypee Brothers.
2. N.N Yalayaswamy. First Aid & Emergency Nursing, CBS publishers.
3. Indian First Aid manual. 7th ed. St. John. Ambulance Association, 2017.
4. Glassey N. Physiotherapy for burns & Reconstruction. Wiley, 2004.
5. Harris N. First Aid and Emergency care, AITBS Publishers.
6. Golwalla A. F. Golwalla S. K. A handbook of emergencies, Jaypee Brothers.

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CERTIFICATE OF ATTENDANCE

presented to

ADHARSH KS (5SU18PT002)

for attending the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID" held from January
2019 till March 2019

Total Hours- 40

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AHAMMED JAREER (5SU18PT003)

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AKASH MOHANAN (5SU18PT005)

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ALAN RAPPAL (5SU18PT006)

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AMRITHA K (5SU18PT007)

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ANASWARA PURUSHOTHAMAN (5SU18PT009)

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ANJALI MURALEEDHARAN (5SU18PT010)

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AVINASH KUMAR (5SU18PT014)

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BLESSY MOL T T (5SU18PT015)

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BORKAR AMISHA VITTHAL (5SU18PT016)

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BRAHMECHA TANVI NARESH (5SU18PT017)

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BRUNDA N M (5SU18PT018)

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CHACKO PRITY PHILIP (5SU18PT019)

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DONA N JESLIN (5SU18PT021)

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FATHIMA THANWEENA (5SU18PT022)

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FAZEELA S (5SU18PT023)

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GOPIKA NANDAN N R (5SU18PT024)

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HAMEED RASHIQUE GANY (5SU18PT025)

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KADAM TRUPTI RAVINDRA (5SU18PT027)

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MEGHNA GIRISH P K (5SU18PT028)

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MERIN RAJU (5SU18PT029)

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MIDHUN YADUBALAN (5SU18PT030)

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MUSSAMMIL ABDULLA (5SU18PT033)

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NAVANEETH VENUGOPAL (5SU18PT035)

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NEHA P K (5SU18PT036)

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SHETTY SAKSHI SHEKHAR (5SU18PT043)

for attending the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID" held from January
2019 till March 2019

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF ATTENDANCE

presented to

SHETTY SHRAJAL PRABHAKAR (5SU18PT044)

for attending the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID" held from January
2019 till March 2019

Total Hours- 40

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Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
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Srinivas University

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CERTIFICATE OF ATTENDANCE

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SHINCE KURIEN PHILIP (5SU18PT045)

for attending the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID" held from January
2019 till March 2019

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SHREYA D S (5SU18PT046)

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Total Hours- 40

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STEEPHAN VARGHESE (5SU18PT047)

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SWATHIKA B R (5SU18PT049)

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Total Hours- 40

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TAMATTA SHANTI CHANDU (5SU18PT050)

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Total Hours- 40

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WAGHMODE RUCHITA SANJAY (5SU18PT051)

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